

CODECHECK Workshops

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A recipe for organizers

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The current version of the recipe is published at
<https://codecheck.org.uk/guide/event-recipe>.

CODECHECK Workshops - A recipe for organizers

This document contains all the lessons learned, do's and don'ts of the four workshops conducted as part of the [CODECHECKing goes NL \(CHECK-NL\) project](#). Its aim is to support everyone who wants to try a CODECHECK workshop and build/support local communities for reproducibility checks.

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Workshop ingredients

- At least 2 enthusiastic organizers (one local and one experienced codechecker)
- At least a dozen participants
- Roughly 1 code submission per 4 participants
- A location with flexible set-up
- Up to a day for cooking

How to prepare

1. Decide on your aims

- a. Who is your audience: classroom (students, early career research training), research group, general or domain specific university audience? Part of a course or a curriculum, or broader target audience (university, or domain)?
- b. Can you offer certificates for attendance/graduate school credits?
- c. Introduction to concepts of reproducibility and codechecking necessary, or advanced tips and skills?
- d. One-shot or community-building?

2. Check your available resources

- a. Who can take care of logistics?
- b. Which rooms are available?
- c. Is there catering you can offer?
- d. Can you offer travel grants?

3. Decide on the flavour

Based on your responses, there are different types or flavours of workshops possible:

- A *full-day workshop* with a broad (domain) scope and inclusive participation requirements (this is the type the project did).
- A more *targeted workshop*, probably also shorter event (addressing specific challenges or career stages of participants).
- Whatever you are willing to try out and *experiment!*

Below, we show the recipe for a full-day workshop (the top-most flavour), assuming that you have secured the resources for a room that can comfortably hold at least 20 participants, and there are funds for at least a shared sandwich lunch.

4. Preparation timeline

As early as possible: contact/recruit a local organizer (in case that isn't you yourself), who knows the venue and how to secure access to the room and catering (yes, this seems very logical, but still important to recall), and together with them, decide on a date.

Ideally **three months before** the workshop: Create the workshop organizing committee. While it is possible to do everything yourself, you probably shouldn't. In our experience, you want to cover the following roles:

- Local organizer: as mentioned above, knows the venue and can arrange access etc.
- Communications lead: creates the registration environment, publishes the advertisements, communicates with (prospective) participants
- Content lead: knows how to do a codecheck (has at least one published) and is comfortable presenting the concept and ideas behind it

Further, why not reach out to the [CODECHECK team](#) to invite a (remote) guest speaker and possible participation in discussion (especially if you feel more comfortable organising than taking the full content lead). We have done live CODECHECKING as part of a workshop. But this is entirely up to you! We are also happy to host a simple website for the workshop.

Two months before the workshop (earlier if you plan to do it during a particularly busy phase of the academic year): publish the registration page and the call for contributions. We used Eventbrite (see [Codecheck - Leiden University](#) for an example) for the registrations and an additional webpage with information on the call (e.g., [CODECHECK-NL Workshop for Digital Humanities on the CODECHECK website](#)). The details on the registration depend very much on the type of workshop you want to run. At the very least, the registration page should contain

- Directions to the venue
- **Contact details** of the organizers; we used an new and dedicated Gmail address for this throughout the project; the experience was not without hassle because multiple people needed access to it; for a one-time workshop, we suggest to use the email addresses of the two organizer roles: the communication lead for any questions about logistics and organization, and the content lead for code submissions and questions about, well, content and codechecking
- Tentative schedule
- Information on catering
- What to bring, e.g., their own laptop with admin rights (!) so they can set up any software they want to check - this is not the case for all employees
- recall that from an AGILE workshop)
- Expected outcomes (codechecks? Of participants or others?)
- Options for travel grants or other certificates
- Implications of no-show

On the latter, we did not have any. This proved to be easier in implementation, but might have led to an increased number of no-shows, which led to too much food waste. At least clearly point out that you will have excess food if people register but do not show up.

Be clear on the **expectations and roles** of the participants: What will they be working on? Can they just sit-in and listen (usually not), do they have to submit code to be checked to participate (no, but highly encouraged to do so!), can they skip part of the workshop (depends)?

For our workshops we had two roles: participants would either submit code to be checked, or join as codecheckers who would work on the code to be checked. The former would still be expected to attend the workshop, to enable a smoother process and increase chances of success.

If your aim is to generate codechecks (in addition to general community-building), depending on the domain or context, you might have difficulties getting submissions to be codechecked. Be very clear about the conditions, requirements, and purpose of these submissions. In our case, these were:

- Code creates the output of some published study (preprint, journal paper, citable report, etc.). No work-in-progress in its early stages (because the certificate needs to relate to a citable object).
- All data is available and open.
- At least one author of the work to be codechecked is present during the break-out groups.

But don't forget to point out the rewards:

- Improved code
- Citable, linkable CODECHECK certificate
- Depending on the publication, a Codecheck badge

Continue advertising, tagging relevant people etc., until you have exceeded the desired number of participants. If you do not get sufficient code submissions, start targeted recruiting in your network.

As a rule of thumb, about 3 to 4 participants per submission are a good ratio. A workshop codecheck can be done by a pair of participants or a group of 5-6, but the fun and the effectiveness are reduced.

About one month before the workshop, the deadline for submissions should close. Depending on your registrations so far, you might want to continue advertising or stop. If you haven't done so during the submission window in a rolling review, now is the time to check the submissions whether they are suitable for a codecheck. If you are in doubt, don't hesitate to reach out to us for advice! Have a look at codecheck.org.uk/nl, however please note that the project Gmail address is NOT monitored anymore! Please use our regular work e-mail addressess.

About one to two weeks before the workshop, send out a pre-workshop survey to learn more about the participants and possibly tailor the workshop accordingly. [add on survey]

How to serve

For the workshop day itself, we recommend that the local organizer has the usual materials ready: textile-friendly **stickers and a marker** so that everyone can write down and wear their names; **outlets** and expansion cables for chargers; a **list of registered participants**; and if budget allows, some (laptop) **stickers** for the collectors among the participants.

A **typical workshop schedule** looked like this (in square brackets which role leads this part):

09:30 Open doors, welcome with coffee

10:00 Official start with round of introductions, information on schedule [communications lead]

10:15 Introduction to codechecking [content lead]

10:45 Live CODECHECK demo with Q&A on process [content lead]

11:15 Create breakout groups [communications lead]

11:30 Codechecks begin in breakout groups [content lead acts as rotating facilitator]

12:15 Lunch break

13:15 Codechecks in breakout groups continue [content lead acts as rotating facilitator]

15:15 Coffee break

15:30 Short reflection from the groups, discussion w/editors

16:30 Closing

We suggest to have a **collaborative document** (e.g., on HackMD) where information can be shared, including participants' names, affiliations, e-mail, and group.

An important aspect to consider is **how to form groups** for the break-out sessions. In our experience, several approaches can work, as long as you prepare them. The pre-workshop surveys can be helpful to decide. The two extremes are obviously to either assign all participants to a group or to have them choose. Our suggestion is to come up with an "ideal" group split based on the survey, and then let participants choose freely. If the groups become too unbalanced, use the "ideal" split as guidance to suggest balancing, e.g., ask all participants to reconsider joining a certain group, or ask specific participants to join. In any case, we suggest that at least one of the author(s) of a work (if present) joins the group codechecking it.

Some criteria for an "ideal" group composition:

- Familiarity with the computing environment/language
- Expertise in the method/domain
- In-group diversity with respect to computing environments (Windows, Linux, Mac, hardware performance) and overall expertise

If a group finishes early because the submitted code works flawlessly on most computing environments, it can be handy to have "spare" CODECHECKS, either from open issues from the CODECHECK website or internal from your organization.

In our experience, the set-up should enable participants to assume "ownership" of "their" codechecking quickly. We have not observed a single group being disinterested in tackling their problem in a collegial way. However, this engagement can decline quickly once the problem is solved, i.e., the code has been successfully checked. Then the nitty-gritty details of writing a short report and submitting it can be tricky to motivate. We recommend to emphasize that the report is written as much as possible during the CODECHECK itself, so that very little remains to be done after the completed CODECHECK.

For an overview of an adapted CODECHECK workflow, see the Appendix of this recipe.

During the **wrap-up**, each group should briefly present how their CODECHECK went. What problems have they encountered, where they successful? Then, a general discussion on the workshop and Codecheck in general can be helpful to exchange further views and experiences. We used Mentimeter as supporting tool during these discussion, but this is not a strong recommendation.

Follow-up/left-overs

As mentioned above, it is important to complete the CODECHECK as much as possible during the workshop. Otherwise, the organizers might end up chasing participants with e-mails to ensure that the CODECHECK is completed and finally registered on the Codecheck website. The content lead should be in charge here.

Lastly, once all the housekeeping is done, we suggest to write a nice blog post about the event and share it widely (at the very least with the participants) and advertise the successful CODECHECKS. Again we would be happy to crosspost it on the CODECHECK website.

Questions?

Don't hesitate to contact the [CODECHECK team](#) and also [people from the Codecheck-NL project](#). Although the project has finished, we are all open science enthusiasts and will continue to be part of the community. Hope to have encouraged you to go for it – Success!

Appendix: Codecheck workflow during workshop

1. **Authors** create a pre-producible workflow: all data and code, plus a readme file detailing the content, a manifest file detailing the output ([CODECHECK configuration file specification](#)), and a license file; this is ideally bundled in a single repository or archive file and accompanied by a (pre-published) paper
2. **Authors** send their request for a CODECHECK to the advertised contact e-mail address

3. The **workshop team** accepts the request for the workshop or advises to follow the normal community workflow
4. During the workshop, **codecheckers** download materials or clone a repository
5. The workshop **codecheckers** create a new directory in their working environment where all new files go, and start documenting the ongoing CODECHECK; exact form of codechecking procedure can vary greatly; there are some optional tools, such as an R package that includes an Rmd template for the report and automates some steps, and templates for word processors to use
6. During a CODECHECK, the workshop **codecheckers** can ask the **authors** (if present at the workshop) in case of encountered problems, keeping in mind the general Codecheck philosophy (especially “the codechecker records but does not fix” – unless it is a very trivial bug like pathnames)
7. The **codecheckers** summarize the process and outcome in a report and bundle it with all input and output files; this workshop CODECHECK bundle is then shared with the **workshop team** via email or repository; the report should at least contain the information on *who* checked *what* and *how* with *which outcomes*; document for future self and other researchers; have a look at the available reports; most contain also optional information (compare [CODECHECK community workflow guide](#))
8. The **workshop team** checks the bundle and report, and together with the workshop codecheckers, revise where necessary; once ready, either the **workshop team** or a corresponding **codechecker** upload the file on Zenodo or OSF.
9. The **workshop team** adds the new CODECHECK to the register in a new issue using this link: <https://github.com/codecheckers/register/issues/new?template=new-community-codecheck.md>.

CODECHECK

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